

ISic3589

Honours for a Iulius

Language

Latin

Type

honorific (?)

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2019-07-19 - Jonathan Prag edited the file based on autopsy and study for 2017 edition

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated in 1971, in room 7 of the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.997856, 14.262463

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory 30600A

Physical Description

Two joining fragments of off-white marble with faint blue-grey veining; height (max) 35.5 cm, width (max) 38 cm, depth 2.7 cm (top edge) reducing to 2 cm (lower edge). The upper margin is intact; the left side has a regular straight cut, but this does not appear to be the original edge to the inscription; the stone is broken to the right and below. One lump of plaster is still attached to the upper part of the front surface. The stone is also engraved on the reverse, with the remains of three lines of Latin letters (see ISic3588), belonging to the mid-third century AD. It appears that the right margin of the later inscription on the reverse is intact, which suggests that the stone was cut down for reuse for the inscription on the reverse; the lump of plaster perhaps belongs to this phase of re-use, when this original face was fixed to a wall or monument.

Dimensions

Height 35.5 cm

Width 38 cm

Depth 2.0-2.7 cm

Layout

Two lines of Latin text are preserved across the lower part of the front face, with a substantial vacat above, which suggests that this is part of the first two lines of the text.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Finely carved letters, with a deep V-cut, broad and regular form, with modest serifs; height 73-75 mm in line 1, reducing in line 2 which is however incomplete. Neat, three-pointed interpuncts are visible wherever word-breaks are preserved.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 73-75 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. [---]· Iulio · [---]
 2. [---]Divi · A[ugusti][---]
- undefined. [---]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy and study for edition of 2017

Translation

Commentary

The last letter of line 1 could be a D, P, or R (no sign of a joining element is visible mid-way down the vertical, but the P or R could be open, which would remove this argument for D). Whether one reads D, P, or R it is difficult to resolve this particular combination as a member of the Julio-Claudian family. It is therefore simpler to assume that the first, larger line contains the name of an honorand in the dative, with the nomen Iulius (either therefore a freedman or a new citizen), and the second line with Divi A[ugusti] perhaps contains a reference, e.g. to flamen divi Augusti, a position attested in Halaesa, both on coinage (RPC I.630-631) and in the epigraphy (cf. ISic3571 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic371>]), and elsewhere in Sicily. It is likely therefore that there is only a single letter missing from the start of line 1 (i.e. the abbreviated praenomen), but if one assumes that the name was centred, and that the second line, which appears slightly more condensed than the first, extended further to the left, then there would be room for "flamini" prior to "divi". The rest of the text might contain further references to the individual's career, and a record of the honouring body, such as "D(ecreto) D(ecurionum)".

The reference to divus Augustus gives a terminus post quem of AD 14. The inscription cannot be closely dated, but is probably Julio-Claudian.

The later inscription ISic3588 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3588>] is on the reverse of this stone.

Digital identifiers:

TM 645668

Bibliography

Prag, J.R.W., Tigano, G. 2017. Alesa Archonidea : il lapidarium. *Introduzione all'archeologia di Halaesa*. Palermo. At no.25

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